

THE DURABILITY OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATE SUBJECTED TO REPEATED LOW VELOCITY IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

Low velocity impact has been considered as quasi-static loading, as the dynamic effects are decaying before the pressure reaches its maximum. However, when the impact energy is low enough as not to cause visible damage, the dynamic effect at the beginning of the impact may cause internal damage to the laminate. Laminates were loaded quasi-statically and by impact to the same bending strain and with the same indenter shape several times. The laminates that were subjected to the impact loading failed much more rapidly. Analysis of the problem shows that the stress waves created by the impact at the beginning of contact, intensify the damage zone created by preceding impact until final failure occurs. On the other hand, repeated quasi-static loading can cause internal damage only as the fatigue characteristic of the material.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are used today in a variety of sophisticated structures like in vehicles, airplanes, etc. In many cases they are the outer skin of the structure and so they are exposed to foreign objects impacted on them. The impact by foreign objects can cause irreversible damage, which affects the residual strength and the durability of the structure. In this article, special attention is devoted to low velocity and moderate mass impact, which may cause undetected damage, that is, no cracks or delaminations were observed after the impact. This kind of damage is very hazardous because there is no noticeable sign for its existence.

The problem of low velocity impact had been addressed by Lord Rayleigh¹ and later by Timoshenko². They showed that if the impact duration is longer than the first harmonic of the target, then quasi-static analysis of the collision can be done. Greszczuk³ extended the solution of Hertz⁴ to the problem of contact stresses of isotropic half space due to spherical indenter, by introducing orthotropic material with transverse isotropy in a plane perpendicular to the impact direction, and using a computer for numerical solution of the stress field.

Sun and Chattopadhyay⁵ extended the solution to plates, and using the momentum law with the deflection of the plate, they were able to calculate the energy and force transfer from the impactor to the target. Greszczuk⁶ considered a case of a flexible target and calculated the energy balance by using analytical and experimental methods. He found that for round plates, the damage is mainly due to bending when the plate is thin and it occurs at the outer surface, while for thick plates the damage is situated inside the plate and is due to the contact stresses. Joshi⁷ found by experiments with sphere impactor, shot by air gun on a composite clamped beam, that visible damage occurs in the distal layers as the bending strain exceeds 9000μ strain. All those experiments suggested that the low velocity impact and quasi-static loading produces the same stress field in the laminates, causing skew cracks under the impactor and vertical crack in the distal layers. When the impact intensity was smaller than certain values, no cracks were initiated.

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The objective of this study is to examine more carefully the difference between impact loading and quasi-static loading.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Specimens of rectangular shape with nominal dimensions of 19x60 mm were cut with a diamond saw from the laminated plates. Three types of plates were used:

1. Graphite/Epoxy T300/5208, $[0,90]_{2s}$ (1mm thick).
2. Graphite/Epoxy AS/3501, $[0,90]_{2s}$ (1mm thick).
3. Glass/Epoxy E/2256, $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ (2mm thick).

Specimens were loaded quasi-statically by three point bending on an Instron testing machine. The support span was 50 mm with 6.35 mm cylinders as anvils, and hemisphere with 12.5 mm radius as indenter (the third point). The impact tests were carried on a drop-weight impact testing machine with the same kind of support and impactor shape. The velocity of the impactor was measured just before striking the specimen by two photo-cells. The force exerted on the impactor was measured by an accelerometer (Kistler) attached to it. Strain gages were attached to some of the specimens on the distal surface. The strain and the acceleration were captured by a Nicolet digital-scope. The weight of the impactor was 0.32 kg while the specimen's weights was under 0.004 kg.

On the first stage of the tests the impact energy, which caused failure, and the corresponding load, measured by the accelerometer, were determined. The equivalent quasi-static tests were performed on the Instron testing machine. The strain to failure was also measured.

On the second stage of the tests, low energy impact loading was repeated on the same specimen until it failed. Loading to the same distal strain level was repeated on the Instron, also until failure.

On the third stage of the tests, again low energy impact loading was repeated, but after a certain number of loadings, the specimen was tested for residual strength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the first stage of the experiments, that is, the quasi-static and impact mechanical properties and strengths, are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1 Quasi-static strength and mechanical properties

Specimen	Initial Modulus GPa	Failure Load N	Strength MPa	Absorbed Energy J	Distal Strain 10^{-6}
Graphite/Epoxy T300/5208	113	400	1655	1.17	11000
Graphite/Epoxy AS/3501	77.5	250	1180	0.63	12000
Glass/Epoxy E/2256	16.9	149	232	0.57	23000
Glass/Epoxy E/2256	16.9	118 _{NF} *			15000

*Glass/Epoxy specimens exhibit nonlinear behavior. This is an intermediate value.

Table 2 Impact strength and failure strain

Specimen	Impact Velocity m/s	Absorbed Energy J	Dynamic Load N	Distal Strain 10^{-6}
Graphite/Epoxy T300/5208	1.85	0.55	238	11000
Graphite/Epoxy AS/3501	1.75	0.52	225	12000
Glass/Epoxy E/2256	1.7	0.46	235	23000

After the determination of the failure loads, a somewhat lower value was chosen for the second stage and repeated for impact and quasi-static loading. A typical impact test output is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Impact test output: Dynamic load and bending strain (distal)

Table 3 shows the results of repeated impact on the specimen until it failed.

For comparison, the same kind of specimens were loaded repeatedly, quasi-statically on the Instron testing machine, up to a level where the distal strain was the same as measured on the impact testing. The loading was repeated up to 10 times, and if the specimen did not fail it was tested for residual strength. The results are shown in Table 4.

It is seen from Tables 3 and 4 that repeated loading to the same strain level at the outer distal surface, caused failure after several times, while quasi-static loading for more times did not. This observation implies that the mechanism of stress build-up in the two methods is different and therefore quasi-static analysis does not reflect exactly the situation on low velocity impact. Referring to Fig. 1 we see that the load oscillates at the beginning of contact as the stress waves propagate and reflect from the opposite surfaces. The level of the load is as high as at maximum deflection when these stress waves had already decayed. Thus, at each impact, contact stresses are developed and propagated through the material, increasing the crack formation and degrading the strength.

Table 3 Failure by repeated impact

Specimen	Impact Velocity m/s	No. of Impacts	Dynamic Load N	Distal Strain 10 ⁻⁶	Residual Strength (MPa)
T300/5208	1.79	2	212	11100	failure
"	1.74	8	206	11000	"
"	1.60	2	208	9600	"
"	1.60	3	220	9600	"
"	1.60	10	195	9600	"
"	1.43	10	181	9200	1448
Glass/Epoxy	1.64	2	234	17400	failure
"	1.64	4	235	17300	"
"	1.61	5	252	16500	"
"	1.26	2	154	14200	"

Table 4 Repeated quasi-static loading

Specimen	Distal Strain (10 ⁻⁶)	Measured Load (N)	No. of Loadings	Residual Strength (MPa)
T300/5208	9600	186	10	1789
"	9600	186	10	1686
AS/3501	11000	214	10	1321
Glass/Epoxy	15000	118	10	191
"	15000	118	10	176

Based on the quasi-static solution for the impact of a beam, the load transfer from impactor to target was formulated and calculated. The expression has the form

$$\left(\frac{F}{k_2}\right)^{2/3} = vt + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 - \frac{1}{m_0} \int_0^t F(\tau)(t-\tau)d\tau - \frac{l^3}{48E_x I} \int_0^t F(\tau)(t-\tau)d\tau$$

where k_2 is the Hertz factor and E_x the effective flexural modulus along the beam. This expression was calculated numerically for the graphite/epoxy laminate and the result is shown in Fig. 2.

Compared with the test result (Fig. 1) we see good agreement with the impact duration and load level, but without the stress waves. Next, the load transfer was calculated without bending the laminate, that is, the last term was omitted. The result is shown in Fig. 3.

This time, the impact duration is much shorter, about 0.5 ms and very close to the oscillations seen in Fig. 1. The load is much higher because the beam was constrained, but the effect of the stress waves is there.

Fig. 2 Bending of graphite/epoxy beam by impact.

Fig. 3 Impact on a graphite/epoxy laminate.

Table 5 Residual strength after repeated impact

Specimen	Impact Velocity m/s	Measured Load (N)	Distal Strain (10 ⁻⁶)	No. of Loadings	Residual Strength (MPa)	Residual Modulus (GPa)
AS/3501	1.6	184	11200	10	997	73.57
"	1.6	178	11600	10	1131	68.07
"	1.6	175	11800	10	1026	66.45
"	1.6	177	11600	10	1097	69.59
"	1.6	172	11300	10	1196	75.54
"	1.6	175	11100	10	1148	78.29
"	1.6	179	11400	10	1044	71.95
"	1.6	178	11400	10	1137	72.50
"	1.6	176	11300	10	1196	73.77
"	1.67	189	11800	10	991	75.67
"	1.67	187	11900	10	1024	75.71
"	1.67	195	11500	9	failure	failure

For examining the durability of the laminates, the third stage of tests were performed by repeated impacts at a somewhat lower level, and then tested for residual strength. Table 5 shows the results. Comparing these results of the AS/3501 with the impact failure data in Table 2 and the quasi-static data in Table 1, we see that by impact with energy which is about 16% lower than the critical one (which causes failure) for 10 times, the strength is degraded by only 5% on the average, and the modulus also degraded only by 5% on the average. On the other hand, the T300/5208 which was impacted on the same ratio (that is, 16% lower impact energy than the critical one), all the specimens failed within the 10 strikes (Table 3). Only when the impact level was lowered by 40%, the specimens sustained 10 strikes without failure and the residual strength was about 88% of the virgin material (Table 3).

The difference between the two graphite/epoxy laminates is mainly the type of fiber which is used, the T300 has a much more higher modulus than the AS in the fiber direction as seen in Table 1, but about the same modulus transverse to the fiber direction. Therefore when the T300 was struck by impact, being more brittle produced more cracks and therefore faster degradation.

CONCLUSIONS

The durability of a graphite/epoxy laminate subjected to low velocity impact imposed transversely on the laminate surface depends mainly on the graphite fiber characteristics and the laminate structure. It was shown that for cross-ply structure, the more brittle fiber could stand less repeated impact and fail much more rapidly than the less brittle fiber.

Comparing the repeated loading of the laminate by impact and quasi-static, it was found that impact is more damaging. As the bending deflections and forces are the same in both loadings, and hence also the contact forces which produce the contact stresses, it is concluded that only the dynamic impact causes the damage, that is, the stress waves preceding the bending. These stress waves changed from compression to tension and back, and so caused rapid cracking of the brittle fibers. Similar phenomena occurred in an angle ply laminate, but the cracking is confined to the matrix, parallel to the fiber direction.

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